

Edward J. Gray (CNRS / DARIAH-EU)

Title: *Building a European Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities : DARIAH-EU Case Study*

Abstract: Launched in 2006 and officially founded as an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) in 2014, DARIAH has long held a place in the SSH Research Landscape. These first years were focused more on the construction of our international research infrastructure and of the various national consortia, as well as policy and advocacy on behalf of our communities. DARIAH also served, and continues to serve, as an excellent incubator for European project grants and the creation of project consortia. In the last two years, however, DARIAH has reached a new phase of maturity, with better organizational processes, developed services, and a stronger network of humanities researchers across Europe and beyond. These efforts are headlined notably by the SSH Open Marketplace and DARIAH Campus platforms, discovery platforms for tools and services, and pedagogical materials, respectively. Joining with the existing, grassroots and researcher-led Working Groups, DARIAH now has multiple means of enabling research in social sciences and humanities in a way that is visible to the individual researcher. DARIAH's evolution presents an interesting use case in building a digital research infrastructure on a European scale, showing how to put in place infrastructural components and know-how to help advance the cause of SSH research in an increasingly digital and changing research landscape.

Marta Abrantes (FCT; ESFRI)

Title: *Funding opportunities for Digital Research Infrastructures and FAIR principles*

Abstract: This presentation will target the funding opportunities in the Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures programme which will be open in 2023 and 2024 and may be of particular interest to the Social Sciences and Humanities scientific community. An introduction regarding the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Portuguese participation in EOSC will be made. This will be followed by the highlight of the opportunities in the calls INFRAEOSC, related to the implementation of EOSC and the application of the FAIR principles. Other opportunities included in the calls INFRADEV and INFRA SERV will also be presented. General remarks about applying to these calls will conclude this presentation.

João Cardoso (FCCN - FCT)

Title: *Funding opportunities for Digital Research Infrastructures and FAIR principles*

Abstract: This communication aims to present and characterize the European Open Science (EOSC) initiative, and what is being done to promote the adoption of EOSC with the Portuguese Scientific Community. With particular focus being given to the perspective of a Research Infrastructure (RI) manager. EOSC aims to promote the development and application of Open Science practices in the European scientific community. As such, there is an ongoing effort to establish a pan European open multidisciplinary network of RI's that work to both provide a network of research data compliant with the FAIR Data Principles and develop services that allow researchers to take advantage of said research data. EOSC is governed through a partnership between the EOSC Association (EOSC-A) and the European Union through the European Commission. Part of EOSC-A's mission is to guarantee the fulfilment of the objectives established in the Memorandum of Understanding for the Co-programmed European Partnership on the EOSC. EOSC-A is also responsible for coordinating the creation of the EOSC ecosystem, combining the efforts of multiple Member States and Associated Countries, through cofinanced projects and other initiatives. Portugal is represented in EOSC-A through FCT, which holds the status of Mandated Organization. As Mandated Organization FCT is responsible for multiple tasks, such as: Acting as liaison between EOSCA and the Portuguese Scientific Community; Defining the National EOSC structure; Promoting the national adoption of EOSC; Coordinating national stakeholders in the adoption of EOSC; Reporting on the national adoption of EOSC; and Disseminating funding opportunities through infra-EOSC calls.

João Mendes Moreira (FCCN - FCT)

Title: *Open Access in Portugal: Landscape and future perspectives*

Abstract: This session contextualizes the main open science/open access activities at national/international level in the last decade, presenting a balance of their implementation and proposals for potential paths to follow in the future.

Paulo Leitão (FCG)

Title: *Metadata aggregation: models and solutions*

Abstract: The production of digital surrogates of heritage collections has characterized, in the last decades, the activity of Libraries, Archives and Museums (LAM's). These digital collections have been stored and made available through individual information systems, different according to the various communities, which has generated more or less hermetic silos that force the user to go through successive access interfaces, each with its own idiosyncrasies. The present situation has led to the search for various solutions, among which those based on the aggregation and manipulation of metadata from the various partners stand out, with the aim to building platforms that enable the integrated access to that universe of metadata, constituting a centralized access point to a multiplicity of contents. This presentation critically discusses the various solutions that have been implemented and refers to some of the new working hypotheses.

Margarida Ramos (NOVA CLUNL)

Title: *Terminology and knowledge organisation: the role of ontologies in digital humanities*

Abstract: In the digital information society era, applying computational methods in the traditional humanities field of study has become a consolidated approach in the current digital research landscape. Terminology, as an interdisciplinary scientific area, goes hand-in-hand with knowledge organisation products, such as information systems and terminological resources. The advent of the Semantic Web, and its underlying formal languages, enables interoperability – in the sense of machine readability – of these information systems, for which recommendations issued by the W3C community (www.w3.org) are at the core of the formal syntax vocabularies used for, among other things, standards compatibility, searchability and reusability. In this presentation, we will discuss how ontologies play a prominent role in knowledge organisation within the theoretical framework of the dual dimension of terminology, namely linguistic and conceptual. Two ontologies will be on display, one designed to organise and formally define the concepts of a given field of interest from the industry, while the other, a modular ontology, is designed to systematise formally – in a 'reason-able' environment – the terms used in a given scientific domain, and corresponding sub-domains, as pointed out by the author of the lexicographical work in focus, namely a legacy dictionary from the 18th century.

George Bruseker (CEO Takin.solutions Ltd.)

Title: *The interplay of infrastructure and data semantics to support the evolution of integrated scholarly/scientific data*

Abstract: The effects of the on-going waves of digital revolution on different structural aspects of research (inputs, outputs, teams, funding, organization methods etc.) cause an on-going challenge for Research Infrastructure systems designed to support, organize and help scholars and scientists take advantage of these innovations. The overarching paradigm of creating and producing research results in digital formats provides a potentially rich and open set of resources for the scholar/scientist to generate and adopt. But, while researchers create new products with new tools, Research Infrastructure struggles to provide all these outputs a home which will sustain them over the long term under such strategies as the FAIR principles. The pragmatic problem is that research generates an incredible diversity of digital outputs both with regards to format as well as content which at any point cannot possibly all be supported and integrated by any individual RI. Semantic data strategies have a role to play in helping RIs to address such questions. In particular, semantics can help clarify a model of the kind of meta-metadata that is required to map the world of researchers, datasets and software that an RI intends to support. Second, clear semantic data workflows and marking of data integration based on workflows can support progressive integration of datasets according to need and ability of organizations, enabling a progressive, decentralized and a-synchronous movement of datasets towards commonly exploitable expression formats enabling a uniform semantic content space. Semantics has an important support role to play in creating a positive interplay between research and research infrastructures in order to generate feedback loops for the generation of ever more integrated and integratable data.

Ricardo Basílio (Arquivo.pt - FCCN-FCT)

Title: *Arquivo.pt: a web archive provider of open data for the Digital Humanities*

Abstract: The Web has, in 25 years, become the primary means for people and institutions to publish all kinds of content and provide access to goods and services. How to access this digital legacy present in websites, blogs, and social networks? This presentation begins by explaining how Arquivo.pt collects and provides access to information preserved from the Web, between 1996 and the present. Arquivo.pt is an open data provider, specifically of Web historical contents. Any researcher may search by text, image, or address (URL) in the public interface of Arquivo.pt. They can also use the Application Programming Interface (API) to automatically process large amounts of information. Next, the types of data and information that can be found at Arquivo.pt and the use cases in the context of scientific research are shown. Those related to the Digital Humanities are highlighted. Finally, the issue of curation

in Arquivo.pt is addressed, referring to the thematic collections and open data sets available on the portal [Dados.gov.pt](https://dados.gov.pt). Curation is understood as a collaborative process in which the community helps to improve the quality of the preserved contents. The presentation ends with a demonstration of the new CitationSaver service (arquivo.pt/citationsaver) that allows researchers to preserve in Arquivo.pt references to Web contents in scientific publications.

ROSSIO Services

Daniel da Veiga Monteiro (ROSSIO Infrastructure NOVA-FCSH)

Nuno Freire (ROSSIO Infrastructure NOVA-FCSH / Europeana Foundation)

Title: *Aggregating data and searching the ROSSIO portal*

Abstract: ROSSIO currently holds metadata about 5.8 million items organised in 55 datasets from 33 cultural heritage and research organisations. We will present an overview of the metadata aggregation process adopted by ROSSIO, and present the key standards and technologies that are the foundation for its sustainable data exchange between the data providers and ROSSIO. We will then follow by presenting the search as a mechanism for submitting requests for simple terms or with restriction filtering on previously aggregated and indexed data. We will present the technologies used in its implementation.

Bruno Almeida (NOVA-FCSH)

Title: *Controlled vocabularies: the case of the ROSSIO Thesaurus*

Abstract: The development of semantic web technologies and linked open data as a paradigm for structuring information on the web brought new interest in controlled vocabularies beyond their traditional role of describing and organising physical collections in memory institutions, namely libraries, museums, and archives. In the case of digital research infrastructures, such as DARIAH and ROSSIO, controlled vocabularies modelled in SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organisation System) could play an important role in linking data provided by different projects and institutions. This presentation provides a brief overview of the vocabulary services of the ROSSIO Infrastructure, which include a tool for modelling vocabularies in SKOS and a platform for the publication of vocabularies as linked open data. These services, managed by NOVA FCSH, are made available to member and partner institutions who want to create and/or publish controlled vocabularies for knowledge organisation in social sciences, arts and humanities, including the academic community and research units of NOVA FCSH.

Ângela Salgueiro (NOVA-FCSH)

Title: *ROSSIO's VRE: a Virtual Research Environment for Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities*

Abstract: Committed to the promotion of scientific and technical innovation, open science, and FAIR principles, ROSSIO Infrastructure (<https://rossio.pt/>) has been an important tool in digital preservation, research reproducibility, scientific dissemination, and social inclusion. Its portal offers several services aiming to support the research community, service providers and the wider public in the Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities (SSAH). One of those services is a Virtual Research Environment (VRE), a working online tool that allows the organisation of resources and the development of collaborative research, strengthening the activities of a *community of practices*. ROSSIO's VRE is a web-based working environment available to registered users that aims to enhance the research experience and streamline the sharing of resources. Following principles of technical interoperability, sustainability, security, and easy-to-use practices, the VRE is a fundamental tool for intuitive Research Infrastructures. In this paper we intend to explain the process behind the creation of ROSSIO's VRE and its main features and commodities (e.g., simple and advanced search, library, annotations, text editor, and sharing), giving the SSAH researchers a comprehensive and sustainable environment for collaboration and resource discovery.

Marco Roque de Freitas (NOVA-FCSH)

Title: *ROSSIO services: exhibitions and collections (NOVA FCSH)*

Abstract: As part of the ROSSIO services panel, this communication aims to present the exhibitions and collections sections offered by Infraestrutura ROSSIO. It will focus on the various production stages, the applied methodologies and benchmarking procedures while acknowledging the basic procedures for the development of digital exhibitions and collections on ROSSIO's Portal.

Amélia Aguiar Andrade (NOVA FCSH)

Researcher in charge of Infraestrutura ROSSIO.

Full Professor in Medieval History at the Faculty of Social and Human Sciences, New University of Lisbon (NOVA FCSH). She has held numerous scientific and university positions, in Portugal and abroad. Since 2011, she has been Director of the Mario Sottomayor Cardia library and the NOVA FCSH Documentation Centers and, since 2016, the National coordinator of DARIAH — The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities and the ROSSIO's Infrastructure Representative. She is also a member of the Scientific Council of NOVA FCSH, including the vice-presidency from 2006 to 2008. From 2009 to 2012, she was Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Social and Human Sciences at the Universidade Nova de Lisboa (NOVA FCSH), for which she received a public praise [DR n° 7599/2012]. She was the coordinator of the doctoral course in history of NOVA FCSH (2011-2013), as well as coordinator of the doctoral course in medieval studies within the framework of a partnership between NOVA FCSH and Universidade Aberta (2016-2018). She headed the Institute of Medieval Studies of the same faculty between 2011 and 2016. Among her international curriculum, it's to highlight that she chaired Scientific Committee of the European Association for Urban History (2012-2014). During her career received 4 awards and honours. Her research areas are related to medieval urban history, the study of spaces and powers in the Middle Ages and their forms of articulation, as well as to the exploration of medieval royal inquiries as a privileged source of treatment for these themes. Participated as Principal investigator in 6 projects and in 23 others as a Researcher. As author and coauthor she published 6 books, 3 exhibition catalogs, 54 chapters of books (14 on international publications), 22 articles in journals and 3 book reviews. She was also the editor of 22 books (3 international). She was part of the organizing committee of 45 events and attended with communication to 83 events (16 as a keynote and 42 by invitation). She is or was the supervisor of 2 Pos-Doc projects, 5 PhD theses and 15 Master dissertations. She was also the co-supervisor of 3 PhD thesis and 1 Master dissertation.

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-9218-6591>

Ciência Vitae: <https://www.cienciavitae.pt/portal/651F-6189-32F3>

Cátia Carvalho (NOVA FCSH)

Head Librarian of the School of Social Sciences and Humanities of NOVA University Lisbon, she has a master's degree in Information Sciences and Digital Libraries, from ISCTE-IUL.

Ciência Vitae: <https://www.cienciavitae.pt/portal/8318-473A-7123>

Ana Paula Figueiredo (DGPC - Directorate-General for Cultural Heritage)

Head of the Archive, Documentation and Library Division / Forte de Sacavém, in the DGPC - Directorate-General for Cultural Heritage. She holds a PhD in Art, Heritage and Restoration from the Faculty of Letters of the University of Lisbon. She was Architectural Heritage Inventory Technician in several institutions that supervised the SIPA (Information System for Architectural Heritage). She taught Art History and was responsible for several training actions, namely History of Tiles and Ceramics.

Ángela Salgueiro (NOVA-FCSH)

Higher Technician at NDDI/NOVA FCSH, Researcher at the Institute of Contemporary History (IHC-University of Évora and NOVA FCSH), holds a degree in History (2006), a master's degree in History – specialization in Contemporary History (2009), and a PhD in History – specialization in Contemporary History (2015), from Universidade NOVA de Lisboa. She is an integrated member of the Institute of Contemporary History (IHC-University of Évora and NOVA FCSH) and was a postdoctoral fellow at the same institution from 2017 to 2019. She works in the Humanities area with an emphasis on Contemporary History, History and Philosophy of Science and Technology and Digital Humanities and collaborates with the ROSSIO Infrastructure since December 2019. The most recent areas of research are Open Science, Responsible Research and Innovation, Data Management, and Research Infrastructures. She is the author of *Science and University in the First Republic* (2018), a book that resulted from the awarded thesis in 2016 by the Mário Soares/EDP Foundation. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8053-4050

Bruno Almeida (NOVA-FCSH)

Higher Technician at the Centre for Digital Development of Research of the Division of Informatics (NOVA FCSH) since April 2022, and integrated Researcher of the Linguistics Centre of NOVA University (NOVA CLUNL) since November 2014. He was a research fellow at ROSSIO Infrastructure – Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities (2020-2022). He completed a Dual Degree PhD Programme between NOVA University and Communauté Université Grenoble Alpes in September 2019 (Doctor in Linguistics by NOVA; Doctor in Information and Communication Sciences by COMUE UGA). His interests include linguistics and information science, especially terminology, knowledge organisation and digital humanities.

Catarina Serpa (Sintra Municipal Archive)

Head of the Culture Division at Sintra City Council, and responsible for designing and overseeing Sintra's strategy for the protection of the historical and cultural heritage, with the aim of transmitting it to future generations and the imperative of making sustainable use of the cultural resources of the territory. She holds a degree in History by the Faculdade de Ciências Sociais e Humanas of the Universidade Nova de Lisboa and is a post-graduated in Art History by the same faculty, having developed all her professional activity in the identification, study, safeguarding and disclosure of the national and local cultural heritage.

Daniel Alves (NOVA FCSH)

Assistant Professor in the History Department and researcher at the Institute of Contemporary History, both at NOVA-FCSH (Lisbon). Holder of a master's degree in 19th century history and a PhD in contemporary economic and social history with the thesis *The Republic behind the counter: Lisbon's shopkeepers and the end of the Monarchy (1870-1910)*, his areas of interest are Contemporary History, Economic and Social History, Urban History, History of Revolutions and Digital Humanities. Author of books and book chapters published on the History of Portugal, as well as articles in national and international scientific journals, especially in Economic and Social History, Historical-GIS and Digital Humanities. He was guest editor in the special issue "Digital Methods and Tools for Historical Research" (2014) of the *International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing* and of the special issue "The History of Retailing on the Iberian Peninsula" (2017) of the *History of Retailing and Consumption*. Editor of the journal *IJHAC: A Journal of Digital Humanities*, Edinburgh University Press, since 2020 (<https://www.euppublishing.com/loi/ijhac>). He collaborates frequently in Digital Humanities projects, namely, in the Atlas, Historical Cartography (<http://atlas.fcs.unl.pt/>) and in the Atlas of Literary Landscapes of Mainland Portugal (<https://litescape.ielt.fcs.unl.pt/>). He has been coordinating the latter since 2018, in collaboration with Natália Constâncio. Has collaborated and / or coordinated projects in the area of digitization and development of digital archives, namely, the project *PTBUILDS19_20 - Portugal Builds - Digital platform for knowledge of the history of constructive cultures in Portugal, 19th-20th centuries* (<https://portugalbuilds.org/>), funded by the Foundation for Science and Technology, since 2019; the project *Digital Archive of Lisbon's Shopkeepers (1870-1974): organization and online availability of the historical archive of UACS* (<http://arquivodigitalcomercio.fcs.unl.pt/>), financed by the Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation, between 2016 and 2017; the project *Heritage and History of the Marble Industry* (<http://marmore-cechap.pt/>), funded by INALENTEJO - QREN 2007.2013 (Operation No. ALENT-08-0347-FEDER-002329), between 2012 and 2015; and the project *DICTIONARIUM - Cartografar as Memórias Paroquias de 1758* (<http://atlas.fcs.unl.pt/>), funded by the POS_Conhecimento program (POS_C644/4.2/C/REG), between 2006 and 2008. Coordinates since 2019 the Digital Humanities Lab at IHC (<http://dhlab.fcs.unl.pt/>) and since 2020 has been Editor-in-Chief of the Portuguese version of the Programming Historian website (<https://programminghistorian.org/pt/>).
Ciência vitae: <https://www.cienciavitae.pt/portal/E710-4069-E339>

Daniel Carapau (FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology)

Science Officer & National Contact Point (NPC) at Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Department of support to R&D Units & Institutions. He completed his PhD in Biochemistry applied to Parasitology from University of Lisbon in 2007. He was a post-doc researcher at the New York University School of Medicine (2008/10) and the Instituto de Medicina Molecular (iMM) of Lisbon (2010/15). Since 2015 he has been working at the main Science-funding Agency in Portugal, Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), with responsibilities varying from the coordination of the publication of the 2020 National Roadmap of Research Infrastructures to Science officer for the Medical and Environmental evaluation panels of the yearly Scientific Employment calls (CEECInd) and of the R&D Units Pluri-annual evaluation. He is one of the National Contact Points for Research Infrastructures under Horizon Europe, and he is the Portuguese representative in the DARIAH ERIC General Assembly.

Daniel da Veiga Monteiro (ROSSIO Infrastructure NOVA-FCSH)

Holder of a degree in Computer Engineering from the NOVA School of Science and Technology, he develops his activity at the NOVA School of Social Sciences and Humanities in the field of architecture of information systems and programming in general.

Delfim Leão (University of Coimbra)

Full Professor at the Faculty of Arts and Humanities from the University of Coimbra. He is currently Vice-Rector for Culture and Open Science at Coimbra University. His main areas of scientific interest are ancient history, law and political theory of the Greeks, theatrical pragmatics, and the ancient novel. He also has a deep interest in Open Science and scholarly communication. He has published around 200 works in international journals, books and book chapters (ORCID: 0000-0002-8107-9165). Among his main recent works are D. Leão et al., *A Man of Many Interests: Plutarch on Religion, Myth, and Magic* (Leiden - Boston, Brill, 2019); D. Leão et al. (eds.), *Our beloved Polites: Studies presented to P.J. Rhodes* (Oxford, Archaeopress, 2022); D. Leão et al. (eds.), *Crises (Staseis) and Changes (Metabolai): Athenian Democracy in the Making* (Firenze, Firenze University Press, 2022). He is a Member of the UNESCO Open Science Advisory Committee, representing UNESCO Electoral Group; of the EOSC Task Force on "Research Careers, Recognition and Credit"; and of the Executive Assembly of OPERAS (ESFRI infrastructure), participating in European projects such as OPERAS-P, TRIPLE, OPERAS-PLUS, PALOMERA.

Edward J. Gray (CNRS / DARIAH-EU)

Research Infrastructure Coordinator at the IR* Huma-Num (CNRS) and the Officer for National Coordination at DARIAH ERIC, the European Research Infrastructure for the Digital Arts and Humanities. He is currently on the Editorial Board for the SSH Open Marketplace, a discovery platform for digital humanities tools and services that was born from the SSHOC Project. He earned his doctorate in history from Purdue University, where his dissertation, "The Marillac: Family Strategy, Religion, and Diplomacy in the Making of the French State during the Sixteenth and Seventeenth Centuries," examined the ways in which familial politics impacted the formation of the early modern French state. While a *doctorant invité* at the École nationale des chartes in Paris, he earned a master's degree in Technologies numériques appliquées à l'histoire (TNAH), where he is also *chargé de cours*. He is also president of the ADEMEC, the *Association des diplômés et étudiants et des Masters de l'École des chartes*. Before working at

Huma-Num, Edward was the Digital Humanities Coordinator at the Maison Européenne des Sciences de l'Homme et de la Société in Lille.

George Bruseker (PHD, Chief Executive Officer at Takin.solutions Ltd.)

PhD, CEO at Takin.solutions <https://takin.solutions>, Co-Chair of CIDOC CRM SIG, Chair of ARM WG. He works and conducts research in the space of semantic data management. His major interests in this area include semantic data workflows, sustainability and the modeling of historical data. He has a PhD from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens in Philosophy (2011) and held an Experienced Researcher Marie Curie at the Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH). He has worked in both academia and industry (museum, cultural heritage and history sectors) on the generation of ontologies and their application to research data. Presently, he is the CEO of Takin.solutions, a semantic data management company working on delivering sustainable semantic data processes and products.

Gonçalo Melo da Silva (NOVA FCSH)

Research fellow at the Institute of Medieval Studies (IEM, NOVA/FCSH) since 2021, with the project MEDDOCS aimed mainly at the digital edition of municipal medieval sources. He is also CO-PI of the project *Think big on small frontier towns: Alto Alentejo and Alta Extremadura leonesa (13th - 16th centuries)* (PTDC/HAR-HIS/3024/2020), funded by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT). Holder of a Ph.D. in Medieval History and a European Ph.D. (NOVA University of Lisbon), his doctoral thesis investigated the urban network, urban landscape and ports in the Algarve in Late Middle Ages (1249-1521). He has a broad interest in various fields ranging from medieval history, maritime history, urban history and religious history to Digital Humanities and Science Communication. He has been a member of several projects (e.g. ROSSIO) and published studies and organised scientific activities related to these themes alone and with other researchers.

Helena Neves (Lisbon Municipal Archive)

Head of division at the Lisbon Municipal Archive. Graduated in History from the University of Coimbra, with a postgraduate degree in Documental Sciences from the same university. She began her professional activity in 1989, at the Lisbon City Council Archive, where she assumed the role of director in 2017.

Ciência Vitae: <https://www.cienciavitae.pt/portal/F81A-8F1A-C834>

Hermínia Vasconcelos Vilar (University of Évora)

Rector of the University of Évora, Full Professor of Medieval History (Department of History, University of Évora). PhD in History / Medieval History (University of Évora - 1998).

Web: <https://www.uevora.pt/pessoas?id=23828>

Ciência Vitae: <https://www.cienciavitae.pt//pt/181C-789D-58C7>

Joana Vieira Paulino (NOVA FCSH)

PhD in History, with a specialisation in Contemporary History (NOVA FCSH, 2019), she had a fellowship from the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology to complete this degree. She has a Master Degree in the same area since 2013 and a Graduation in History from the same institution since 2010. She is currently a researcher in the Institute of Contemporary History (NOVA FCSH/IN2PAST), where she works as a junior researcher in the Digital Humanities Lab. She participated in several projects (among them, the ROSSIO Infrastructure, as a digital humanist), in multiple international conferences, and has several publications among her research interests - Social and Mentalities History, Child Welfare, Urban History and Digital Humanities. She won the 1st Cascais History Award - Ferreira de Andrade and the 3rd Prize for Young Researchers from ADEH.

João Cardoso (FCCN - FCT - Scientific Computing Unit of the Foundation for Science and Technology)

João Cardoso is a Data Manager at FCCN since 2021. His functions are split between managing the national adoption of EOSC, and defining policies and services for RDM, in the context of the Polen initiative. Between 2013 and 2020 he was an intern researcher at INESCID, where he collaborated in several research projects in the area of RDM. He holds a MSc in Telecommunications and Informatics Engineering from IST (2013), and is currently finishing his PhD programme in Computer Science Engineering also from IST (2023).

CIÊNCIA-ID: 2012-B202-C893

ORCID: 0000-0003-0057-8788

João Mendes Moreira (FCCN - FCT - Scientific Computing Unit of the Foundation for Science and Technology)

Director of the Scientific Information Area, Unit FCCN, Foundation for Science and Technology of Portugal (FCT). This area's main mission is to provide access to recognized and prestigious scientific information sources (**b-on** initiative), to promote, support and facilitate open science practices (**Institutional Repositories**, **Scientific Journals** and **Research data**) and facilitate the management and access to information on science and technology in Portugal (**PTCRIS** initiative). Over the past two decades, he has developed and delivered, directly or indirectly, infrastructures and services for the research and education community. He is/was member of several committees and working groups of which stand out the following: National Point of Reference (NPR) on Scientific Information (European Commission) and FCT Representative on the **European Open Science Cloud Association**

<https://www.cienciavitae.pt//pt/2E13-6710-9928>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9081-2728>

Marco Roque de Freitas (NOVA-FCSH)

Visiting Assistant Professor (Musicology department, NOVA FCSH). Completed his PhD in Ethnomusicology in May 2019 under the program *Doctor Europaeus*. Currently, he is a Visiting Assistant Professor at NOVA FCSH and collaborates with ROSSIO Infrastructure: Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities. His academic production focuses mainly on three themes: 1. Nation-building and nationalism in postcolonial Africa; 2. Expressive behaviour, gender, and sexuality; and 3. History of Ethnomusicology. He has published two books, including *A Construção Sonora de Moçambique (1974–1994)* (Kulungwana, 2020; Sistema Solar, 2023).

Margarida Lages (Diplomatic Institute)

Head of Archives and Library of the Diplomatic Institute of the Portuguese Ministry of Foreign Affairs since March 2012. She has a degree in History from the Faculty of Social and Human Sciences of the Universidade Nova de Lisboa (FCSH-NOVA) and in Arts Management from the Institute of European Studies of Macau. She has been a visiting Professor of the Master "Cultural Practices for Municipalities" - Document Management Seminar (History Department of the FCSH-NOVA) and a PhD student in Portuguese Studies, specializing in Cultural Studies at the FCSH-NOVA. She is responsible for editing the work of Eduardo Prado Coelho and she is decorated as official of the Order of Merit (Portugal). Previously, she has had the following positions: Assessor of the Secretary of State for Culture (1985-1987); Advisor Portuguese Institute for Book and Reading (1987-1989); Assistant to the area of literature and theater Commissariat for Europalia 91-Portugal (1989-1992); Advisor to the Commissioner General of the National Commission for the Commemoration of Portuguese Discoveries (1992-1995); Advisor to the area of the theater, Lisbon 94 (Lisbon European Capital of Culture) (1993-1994); Service Director for Planning and Coordination in the Camoes Institute (1995-1997); Advisor to the Foundation Committee of the Macao Cultural Centre (1998-1999); Head of Division of the Book and Promotion of Reading in the Portuguese Institute for Books and Libraries (2000-2003); Head of Division of the Documentation and Information Centre in The Portuguese Institute for Aid Development (2003-2008); Chief of Staff of the City council Manuela Júdice (2008-2009); Responsible for the archives of the Portuguese Institute for Aid Development (Oct. 2009- March 2012).

Margarida Ramos (CLUNL - Linguistics Research Centre of NOVA University Lisbon)

Researcher at the Linguistic Centre of NOVA University of Lisbon (CLUNL), within the LLT group (Lexicology, Lexicography and Terminology). Holder of a PhD in Linguistics – Lexicology, Lexicography and Terminology – from the NOVA University Lisbon, and in Sciences de l'Information et de la Communication by the Université Savoie Mont Blanc (Dual Phd degree programme), she has collaborated with the Linguistics Center of NOVA University Lisbon as a Doctoral Fellow, within the Knowledge, Representation and Use (KRUse) programme, granted by the Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) of the Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education (MCTS), and at the Laboratoire d'Informatique, Systèmes, Traitement de l'Information et de la Connaissance (USMB). She is a member of IPQ's CT 221 Terminologia, Língua e Linguagens and of ISO TC 37, Language and Terminology. Her research interests focus on terminology, ontologies, lexicography, and corpus linguistics. She is currently a member of the project MORDigital – Digitisation of the Dicionário da Língua Portuguesa by António de Morais Silva [PTDC/LLT-LIN/6841/2020], whose focus is a legacy dictionary.

Maria Margarida Lopes (National Library of Portugal)

Deputy Director-General of the National Library of Portugal since 2020. Between 2015 and 2020 she coordinated the Management Support and Special Projects Office, collaborating in the management of several national digitisation projects and in the NLP participation in European projects like Europeana. From 2012 to 2015, she was the Head of the Diffusion and Co-operation Projects Service at the National Library of Portugal. Graduated in History in 1993 and post-graduated in Library and Information Science in 1996, she holds an Advanced Course in Public Administration (2003) and Public Management (CAGEP, 2021). She is currently a PhD student in Public Policy at ISCTE-IUL, with a dissertation project on the impact of the EU on digital transformation policies for cultural heritage in Portugal.

Marta Abrantes (FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology, ESFRI - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures)

Science officer at FCT and Delegate and National Contact Point (NPC) for the Horizon Europe Programme Committee on Research Infrastructures. She has a 5-year degree in Biochemistry from the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon (UL), holds a master's degree in Pharmaceutical Chemistry from the Faculty of Pharmacy of UL and a PhD in Microbial Biology, from the Institute of Biological and Chemical Technology – New University of Lisbon. She joined the Department of International Relations of the Foundation for Science and Technology in 2013 and since then she has worked in different FP7 and Horizon 2020 projects and has closely followed and participated in several European Research Infrastructures in which Portugal participates. Presently she's a national delegate for the European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures - ESFRI, and a national delegate and National Contact Point for the Horizon Europe Programme Committee on Research Infrastructures.

Nuno Freire (ROSSIO Infrastructure NOVA-FCSH / Europeana Foundation)

Holder of a PhD in Informatics and Computer Engineering from the University of Lisbon. He works in the development of the ROSSIO Infrastructure (NOVA-FCSH) and also works at the Europeana, with research interests in novel methods for data aggregation, data quality and data modelling for the maintenance and evolution of the Europeana Data Model. His main domain of interest is his cultural heritage and digital humanities.

Paulo Jorge Oliveira Leitão (FCG - Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation)

Director of the Public Library “Marquesa de Cadaval”. Head of Cultural Division in Almeirim Municipality, Portugal. Head of Libraries Division in Almada Municipality, Portugal. Director of Innovation and Development Services in the National Library of Portugal. Head of Information Systems Department in the Art Library of the Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation, Portugal. Former Member of the Standing Committee of IFLA Art Libraries Section and member of Art Discovery Group Catalogue. Professor of information studies in Nova University, Lisbon, Portugal. He is holder of a Degree in History from the University of Lisbon (1983). Postgraduate in Documentation from University of Lisbon (1990). Master’s in information studies and Digital Libraries from ISCTE (2000). Phd in Information Science from the University of Évora (2014). Phd in Contemporary History from Nova University (2022).

Ricardo Basílio (Arquivo.pt / FCCN-FCT - Scientific Computing Unit of the Foundation for Science and Technology)

Web curator at arquivo.pt (the Portuguese Web archive service, operated by the Scientific Computing Unit of the FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology) where he is in charge of the training program (arquivo.pt/training). Member of the Content Development Working Group of the International Internet Preservation Consortium in which he is the lead curator of the “Street Art” collection. Was part of the ROSSIO Infrastructure for Digital Humanities research team between 2018 and 2022. Holds a Master's degree in Documentation and Information Sciences from the Faculdade de Letras of the Universidade de Lisboa. Worked at the Biblioteca de Arte of the Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian and at the NOVA-FCSH library. His area of interest is digital preservation.

Silvestre Lacerda (DGLAB - Directorate-General for Books, Archives and Libraries / ANTT - Torre do Tombo National Archive)

Director-General of the DGLAB - Directorate-General for Books, Archives and Libraries and Director of the ANTT - Torre do Tombo National Archive. Degree in History from the Faculty of Letters of the University of Oporto, with a specialization course in Documental Sciences, option Archive, by the Faculty of Letters of the University of Coimbra. He is a member of the Association of Latin American Archives and the Intergovernmental Committee of Iberarchives. He represents Portugal on the European Board of National Archives and, since 2016, is the Chairman of the Committee of Experts of the UNESCO National Commission on the Memory of the World Programme.

Teresa Barreto Borges (Portuguese Cinematheque / Museum of Cinema)

Coordinator of the Documentation and Information Centre of the Cinemateca Portuguesa - Museu do Cinema since June 1998. Degree in Media Studies (scientific branch), Faculdade de Ciências Sociais e Humanas / Universidade Nova de Lisboa (1989-1994); Postgraduate degree in Documentation Sciences (Library branch), Faculdade de Letras / Universidade de Lisboa (2003-2005).